

Embedded Sensors for Composite Structures

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ABSTRACT

Optical sensors embedded in composite structures can be used to produce valuable data regarding the structure's current load state as well supply information about the structure's health. Fabricating such a system offers many interesting challenges in the areas of sensor design, fabrication and in choosing the architecture that is best used in composite materials. We address the benefits of composite structures with sensors, sensor designs for collecting data in a composite structure and multiplexing systems for effectively distributing sensors throughout the structure. In addition, we address the effects of the embedded sensor on composite material properties and identify the proper location and orientation of the sensors.

Keywords: Material Properties, Fiber Optic Sensor, Embedded Sensor, Multiplexing

BENEFITS OF SENSORS IN STRUCTURE

Several benefits can be realized by embedding fiber optic sensors in composite structure. These benefits can be grouped under the general headings of integrity characterization and load response monitoring. Structural damage detection and classification, as well as monitoring of overall health of the structure are included under the heading of integrity characterization. Load response monitoring includes the ability to obtain real time feed-back of the structure's current state, accurately track and record the life cycle load history.

INTEGRITY CHARACTERIZATION

Sensors embedded into composite materials can be used to detect damaging impacts and fatigue cracks in a structure [1]. These same sensors can be used as a receiver for a propagating wave sent into the structure, to determine location and extent of delaminations within the composite. Both of these capabilities can be used to characterize the integrity of the structure. The ability to perform an in-situ characterization of the structure's integrity or "health" reduces the cost of maintaining composite structure by limiting the number of scheduled maintenance periods and limiting the need to remove the structure from service to perform inspections. In large structures, cost savings can also be realized by reducing the inspection area using embedded sensors that indicate location of defects.

LOAD RESPONSE MONITORING

Information from sensors provides real time feedback of a structure's current load state to accurately track and record the life cycle load history of the structure. An accurate record of this history insures that the structure is utilized to the complete limit of its fatigue life. This approach often reduces replacement costs by eliminating the need to rely on conservative life cycle schedules derived from models. Removing the reliance on conservative models can extend the useful life of the structure by providing a direct measure of fatigue life. In addition, load response monitoring in conjunction with a testing program can be used to verify and enhance the accuracy of structural models. Finally, load data can be used to obtain damage information by monitoring changes in load path or modal response.

SENSOR DESIGN

Sensors for integrity and load response monitoring must be multiplexed [2] to limit the number of locations from which the sensor leads egress the structure. Also, the sensors must be small enough so that the mechanical properties of the composite materials in which they are embedded are not adversely affected. In addition, the sensors must be robust enough to survive the manufacturing process while still retaining the sensitivity, range and frequency response required to perform the desired task.

Resistive Foil Strain Gauge

As a baseline, we chose a foil resistive strain gauge as shown in Figure 1. There are several characteristics that make this sensor undesirable for embedded applications. The physical size of the gauge itself and egress path of the four sensor leads have detrimental effects on the composite materials mechanical properties. The high processing temperatures of the embedding process make it difficult for the strain gauge to survive the embedding process. Also, the sensor

Figure 1.

is difficult to calibrate, is prone to spurious results due to electromagnetic interference, and is prone to failures. These problems represent a considerable life cycle maintenance cost to an embedded sensor.

Piezoelectric Sensors

We have also considered sensors that rely on the piezoelectric effect to obtain strain or acceleration readings [3]. Although PZT (Lead Zirconate Titanate) ceramic sensors solve the calibration and failure problems of resistive foil strain gauges, they still suffer from a similar problem of damage during fabrication, and affect a laminate's mechanical properties due to physical size and multiple sensor leads. In addition, the Curie temperatures of the PZT ceramics are considerably lower than the processing temperatures of most aerospace composite resin systems. We had considered poling the ceramic after the PZT was embedded in the laminate, however, the large voltages coupled with the dielectric properties of carbon composite laminates make this a difficult task. A final concern with the piezoelectric sensor is its poor response to low strain rates.

Optical Fiber Sensors

Our investigation of candidate embedded sensors for structural integrity and load response monitoring has led us to select optical fiber sensors. Optical fiber sensors such as the one shown in Figure 2 offer four major advantages over resistive foil or piezoelectric strain gauges. The optical fiber sensors are considerably smaller (125 μ m diameter) than the previously discussed sensors that ranged between 40 mm and 250 mm in diameter. The sensors can be designed in conjunction with a multiplexing system architecture so that several sensors can be incorporated into a single optical fiber. This improves the mechanical properties of the laminate (for a given number of embedded sensors) due to the reduced number of sensor leads that are required to egress from the structure. In addition, a sensor fabricated from a properly selected optical fiber demonstrates excellent survivability with regard to the temperature, pressure, and handling

Figure 2.

during composite laminate processing operation. Finally, sensors that measure environmental phenomena through the use of purely optical signals are not subject to electromagnetic interference as are resistive foil strain gauges and piezoelectric transducers. Electromagnetic interference issues can severely degrade a sensor's ability to present structural information for "in-service" conditions.

Several optical fiber sensor designs including Michelson [4], Mach-Zehnder [5], and microbend [6] were considered prior to selecting intrinsic [7] and extrinsic [8] Fabry-Perot sensors and Bragg Grating sensors [9]. These sensors were selected because their outputs are not effected by intensity fluctuations due to other phenomena, do not rely on a reference leg, can be multiplexed, and survive the manufacturing process.

MULTIPLEXING SYSTEMS

In the interest of minimizing ingress/egress holes in a structure for a given number of sensors, it is desirable to multiplex several sensors on a single optical fiber. Optical fiber sensors have several techniques by which they can be multiplexed. Multiplexing techniques typically use one of the properties associated with the optical signals, such as its polarization state, coherence, relative position (time), wavelength, and frequency. Polarization and frequency division multiplexing techniques have a limited number of distinct, resolvable states which in turn limit the number of sensors that can be multiplexed. Therefore we have selected time (position), wavelength, and coherence division multiplexing techniques.

Time Division Multiplexing

Time division multiplexing is a technique based on sending very narrow pulses of light into an optical fiber. Optical pulses launched into an optical fiber will reflect off a given sensor in an optical fiber string and return to a detector in a predictable amount of time. By gauging the time of flight that it takes this optical pulse to return, sensor signals are discriminated. Sensors must be spaced on the order of a meter apart, based on the state-of-the art for optical pulsing.

Wavelength Division Multiplexing

Wavelength division multiplexing involves tailoring individual sensors in an optical fiber string to respond to different wavelengths. The optical system architectures are designed to include each of the wavelengths that have been assigned to the individual sensors. Single wavelengths from the multiple wavelengths traveling in an optical fiber are then deconvolved through the use of wavelength filters. After the wavelengths have been sorted, the signal conditioning of the individual sensor responses is performed.

Coherence Multiplexing

Coherence multiplexing uses the phenomenon of a finite measurable phase difference between two propagating light signals to spatially discriminating individual sensors. The individual sensors are uniquely characterized by assigning each a different optical cavity length. By matching the coherence of the optical signal in the demodulation system for each sensor, an accurate determination of the sensor's 'environment' is obtained. The sensors are interrogated serially in time, and the process is repeated for a continuous map of the environment.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES

One primary rationale for selecting optical fiber sensors to perform structural integrity characterization and load response monitoring is their inherently small size. The size of these devices lends itself to embedding in composite material without detrimental effects to the host material. Thick validation specimens were fabricated with embedded optical fiber sensors and tested in interlaminar shear, flexure, tension, and compression. The arrays of optical fiber

sensors were embedded parallel and perpendicular to the reinforcement fibers and in several different depths within the laminate. Test specimens containing optical fiber sensors were compared to baseline specimens without an observed alteration of the strength baseline.

LOCATING SENSORS

Optical fiber sensors, with their unique embeddability characteristics, can be used to obtain information through the thickness of a laminate. This allows measurements of load response and structural integrity to be made without interpolation between conventional surface mounted gauges. Embedded sensors can detect non-linearities, classical lamination theory degeneration, and irregular loads not intelligible to surface mounted devices. For sensor placement, it is imperative that the optical fiber sensors be located parallel to reinforcement fibers to minimize optical signal loss, and to ensure that the primary measurement axis of the optical fiber is aligned with the primary loading axis within a particular lamina of the laminate. Ingress/Egress of the optical fiber sensors into and out of the structure is also an important issue in that, signal loss must be considered, small bend radii can result in breakage, and the fiber must be protected at the point in which it exits the structure.

CONCLUSIONS

Optical fiber sensors embedded in composite materials offer many unique advantages over conventional surface mounted health and load monitoring devices in terms of performance increases, information obtained, and "smart structure" manufacturing ability. The optical fiber sensors do not have a deleterious effect on the mechanical properties of the laminate, optical fiber sensors demonstrate excellent survivability with regard to the temperature, pressure, and handling associated with composite laminate fabrication, and these sensors are not subjected to electromagnetic interference. Optical fiber sensors have several techniques by which they can be multiplexed, limiting the number of leads for each sensor. Finally, optical fiber sensors are used to obtain information throughout the thickness of a laminate, allowing measurements of load response and structural integrity to be made without interpolation between conventional surface mounted gauges. Embedded sensors can detect non-linearities, classical lamination theory degeneration, and irregular loads unintelligible to surface mounted devices.

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